

Whether Pushing or Pulling an Industrial Trolley Reduces Worker Stress : A Physiological Study¹

Mohamed Eltarabelsi

Research Scholar, Department of Industrial Design Engineering, University of Karabük,
Turkey

Suat Altun

Professor and Head of the Department of Industrial Design Engineering, University of Karabük,
Turkey

Abstract

Pushing and pulling a moving trolley in industries or warehouses is a common cause of injury. The aim of this study is to investigate whether pushing or pulling leads to reduced stress in workers through the use of physiological effects, particularly heart rate. Thirty employees worked pushing and pulling industrial trolley. Results: The average heart rate (HR) during pushing was the same as that during pulling, there was no statistically significant difference. Conclusion: Pushing an industrial trolley has the same effect on HR as pulling it. Injuries during pushing or pulling activities carry equal risk.

Keywords

Pushing, Pulling, Musculoskeletal Disorders, Heart Rate, Ergonomics.

1. Introduction

Pushing, and pulling a movable trolley in industry or warehouses are the principal sources of injuries from simple cuts, bruises, and sore muscles to more serious conditions or chronic disorders. Musculoskeletal disorder (MSDs) injuries or illnesses that result from overexertion or repetitive motion represent a major problem in modern occupational environments. The total number of cases of work-related MSD in 2021-2022 was 477,000 in Great Britain [1]. Pushing and pulling activities during manual material handling are associated with MSDs injuries and lower back injuries, which create a different type of force on the spine than lifting tasks. The overuse of pushing and pulling usually causes pain in the back, wrist, forearm, elbow, upper arm, and shoulder regions [2]. Pushing and pulling involve applying hand force horizontally, pushing away from the body and pulling towards the body. Push and pull forces can be defined by three distinct factors. First, the initial force is needed to initiate the movement of an object. Second, there is the sustained force, which is a lesser force necessary to maintain the object's movement. Finally, there is a stopping force, which is required to halt the movement of the object. In this study, for short-distance pushing, the initial force is selected.

¹Address Author Correspondence to Mohamed Eltarabelsi
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2. Literature Review

Currently, it remains uncertain which action, pushing or pulling, should be prioritized. Likewise, the ideal handle heights for pushing and pulling are still undetermined [3]. Pulling tasks involving a trolley resulted in a notable increase in muscle activation compared with tasks involving pushing the cart. Moreover, a significantly higher level of perceived exertion was observed in pulling than in pushing [4]. A previous study reported that the strengths required for pushing were greater than those required for pulling [5,6]. These disparities in strengths between pushing and pulling could be attributed to variations in the study populations, study design (including instructions given to subjects or the equipment used to measure forces), and/or variances in body postures and techniques employed. The initial and sustained maximum acceptable forces for pulling tasks were 13% and 20% lower than those for pushing tasks; however, this difference was not deemed statistically significant [7]. When carts of equal weight are pushed, an average of 93.5% of the force required for pulling is needed [8]. Psychophysical methodology applied to a treadmill experiment revealed that the maximum allowable weight was lower for pulling than for pushing [9]. Biomechanical analysis revealed an increase in shear forces on the lumbar spine during pulling activities, whereas a reduction was found during compression activities [10]. Additionally, pulling tasks on steeper slopes resulted in greater compression and shear forces than pushing tasks did. According to previous studies, it is still unclear whether pushing or pulling an industrial trolley results in fewer injuries.

3. Research Objective and Methodology

3.1. Research objective

The aim of this study is to investigate the physiological effects, particularly HR. HR analysis helps assess the intensity of body movement during tasks. A reduction in heart rate is associated with reduced energy output and reduced muscle activity. For the purpose of this study, HR measurement was chosen to evaluate the differences in effort required when pushing and pulling an industrial trolley.

3.2. Method

3.2.1. Participants

A total of 30 healthy subjects, 15 males and 15 females, participated in this study while pushing/pulling an industrial trolley. The age of the participants was between 18 and 30 years. Anthropometric data were collected for all participants; the average stator height was 169.16 ± 2.24 cm, the average weight was 66.50 ± 5.69 kg, and the elbow standing height was 102.9 ± 1.50 cm.

3.2.2. Apparatus

1. The industrial trolley was equipped with horizontal push handles at heights of 64, 95 and 105 cm above the ground, four swivel castors with a diameter of 12 cm and a steel platform

measuring 90 x 60 cm for carrying loads. The industrial cart carries a load of 130 kg and the total weight of the cart with the load is 140 kg, as shown in Figure 1.

2. A wireless device from Wahoo (Ticker 2X) [11] was used to measure participants' HR beats per minute. This device consists of two parts. The first part, the signaling device, is attached to the participant's chest near the heart. The transmitting device measures the HR, records it in the device and then sends the reading to the second part (a smartphone with Wahoo software).
3. The participants received brief instructions on how to carry out the experiments and were shown where to stand in the foot position on the marked floor and how to push/pull the trolley. The participants confirmed that they had no history of back pain, musculoskeletal disorders, heart disease, or other health problems that could have negatively impacted task results.

3.3 Consent form

1. The participants signed an informed consent form to participate in this study. The participants understood the task flow and knew how to carry out and stop the experiments at any time.

Figure 1: Pushing an industrial trolley

3.4. Pushing an industrial trolley

The participants pushed and pulled an industrial trolley with horizontal handle heights of 64, 95, and 105 cm over 76 m and 21 m, respectively. The participants wore the heart rate device (ticker 2X) around their chest and began pushing or pulling when the HR was normal (at rest). For each task, three HR measurements were taken while pushing or pulling and the average of these measurements was recorded. The same procedure was used when pushing/pulling over a distance of 21 m.

4. Results and Analysis

4.1 Experiments 1

Pushing an industrial trolley, a distance of 76 meters. The average HR results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Heart rate results of pushing an industrial trolley.

<i>Participants average HR measurement (beats per minute)</i>					
Pushing trolley			Pulling trolley		
Task 1	Task 2	Task 3	Task 4	Task 5	Task 6
94.80	92.66	91.80	94.33	90.90	90.33

The average HR for Task 1 is 94.80 beats per minute, which is the highest for pushing a trolley with a handle height of 64 cm, and the lowest HR is 90.33 beats per minute for Task 6, which is pushes a trolley with a handle height of 5.5 cm and includes 105 cm for pulling. The HR comparisons shown in Figure 2 between Task 1 Pushing and Task 4 Pulling for all 30 participants are nearly identical, and there is a very small difference of 0.47 as reported in Table 3. For tasks 2 and 5: there was an obvious difference of 1.76 and the average HR when pulling was lower than when pushing. The same case applies to Task 3 and 6, where there is a slight difference between pulling and pushing; pulling a cart takes 1.47 less than pushing it does, as shown in Table 2.

Figure 2: Participants' heart rate of T1 pushing versus T4 pulling.

Analysis of variance revealed that the P value = 0.499. Therefore, there is no significant difference between them. The Tukey's test revealed that there was no difference between the means of the combination task for T1--T2, T3--T4 and T5--T6. However, there were no significant differences between pushing and pulling tasks T1--T4, T2--T5, or T3--T6.

Table 2: Pushing versus pulling differences for a distance of 76 m.

#	Task	Handle height	Average HR pushing	Average HR pulling	Differences
1	T1-T4	64 cm	94.80	94.33	0.47
2	T2-T5	95 cm	92.66	90.90	1.76
3	T3-T6	105 cm	91.80	90.33	1.47

4.2. Experiment 2

An industrial trolley; was pushed a distance of 21 meters. The average HR results are shown in Table 3. The average HR for Task 2 was 91.37 and was highest when a cart was pushed. In task 5, the lowest HR was 89.87, i.e. when a trolley with a handle height of 95 cm was used. The average HR

difference between Task 1 pushing and Task 4 pulling was 0.27. These results show that there is a slight increase in pulling over pushing compared with other handle heights, which is due to the low trolley handle height of 64 cm, which requires the participant's body to bend downward, to reach the trolley handle the muscles. The activity of the lower limbs, especially the thigh muscles, increases. There was a small difference between Task 2 and Task 5 and between Task 3 and Task 6; When the cart was pulled, the average HR was 1.5 and 1.07 lower than when the industrial trolley was pulled, as shown in Tables 3 and 4.

Table 3: Heart rate results of pushing an industrial trolley.

<i>Participants average HR measurement (beats per minute)</i>					
Pushing trolley			Pulling trolley		
Task 1	Task 2	Task 3	Task 4	Task 5	Task 6
90.66	91.37	90.10	90.93	89.87	89.03

Statistical analysis revealed that the P value was 0.958, indicating that there was no significant difference. There were no significant differences between Pushing and Pulling Task 1-Task 4, Task 2-Task 5, or Task 3-Task 6. In Figure 3, the approximate heart rates during push/pull are nearly identical.

Table 4: Pushing versus pulling differences for a distance of 21 m

#	Task	Handle height	Average HR pushing	Average HR pulling	Differences
1	T1-T4	64 cm	90.66	90.93	0.27
2	T2-T5	95 cm	91.36	89.86	1.5
3	T3-T6	105 cm	90.10	89.03	1.07

Figure 3: Participants' heart rate at T1 versus T4 pushing.

The statistical results revealed that there was no significant difference between pushing and pulling. Notably that pushing tasks with cart handle heights of 95 cm and 105 cm require a slightly higher average HR than pulling tasks do. Nevertheless, this inequality lacks statistical significance. In addition, some previous studies that used different criteria and instruments reported no significant

differences in maximum isometric strength [12,13]. In this experiment, pushing had the same effect on HR as pulling. Importantly there may not be a significant difference in HR between pushing and pulling an industrial cart. This could be because both activities require similar effort.

5. Conclusion

The results of the study suggest that there is no statistically significant difference between the actions of pushing and pulling an industrial trolley via the physiological approach. These results are consistent with previous psychophysical research [12,13,3] and suggest that the similarity in HR is due to the same physical effort and muscle strain required for both tasks. Musculoskeletal injuries related to pushing and pulling share similarities. It is not advisable to prefer pulling over pushing or vice versa. They have the same risk of injury, so caution should be exercised when pushing or pulling with different loads, the weight of the industrial trolley, the distance traveled and the individual's physical fitness, frequency and handle heights. Ergonomics recommended occupational safety guidelines for pushing and pulling tasks outlined by reputable organizations such as the National Institute of Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH) [14]. Pushing and pulling activities can be carried out safely when performed correctly and with the right technique. Further research is needed to examine the effects of compressive forces on the lower back using psychophysical and biomechanical measures.

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